

History of Psychology in Turkey

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Abstract

Psychology in Turkey may have considered beginning with Avicenna, Ghazali and Farabi during the Seljuk and Ottoman Empires, because at those times, mental health was given importance, and some special healings were applied to the patients. However it is more likely that during the period of Mehmet the second, in the 15th century, a special hospital was built for the people who have mental illnesses. Patients were healed by music and sports. Today's sense of psychology studies began in 1915 in İstanbul University. The guest professors from

Germany came to give lectures. After World War 1, foreign professors returned to their countries and Şekip Tunç became the head of the chair of psychology. He had completed his education in Jeanne Jacques Rousseau Institute. He had authored many articles and translated some of the works of Freud and James.

Muzaffer Şerif, Şekip Tunç, Mümtaz Turhan are some of the other first psychologists that have served and contributed to the psychology field in Turkey. After 1960 the psychology departments in the universities began increasing. When the year 1987 came, the number of the students increased as well. The investigations and the articles written are also increased. By the efforts of the 'Psychologists Association' new attributes to the definition of the psychology profession were made. The definition of the functions and responsibilities of the psychologists are defined clearly and are indicated where they may work. When the standards of education in psychology is the subject, APA standards indicate some rules.

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Today, psychology has come a long way and recently we have many important psychologists in Turkey who contribute to the field. However this area still needs to be improved and worked on a lot more, in order to meet the needs of people that live in today's life full of adversities.

Keywords: Psychology, Turkish psychology history, counseling and guidance, interdisciplinary, mental health professionals, academic research

Introduction

Psychology is one of the disciplines that is quite ancient. People have been interested in the nature of their own attitudes for so many years. In the fourth and fifth centuries, Plato, Aristotle and the other philosophers have asked many questions and tried to find out the answers about human behavior. This situation indicates an unbreakable bond between the past and today. So psychology is one of the oldest and one of the newest disciples as well. What separates modern psychology from the old previous ones are the methods that it uses today. Investigators today use controlled observation and experiments in order to answer human's attitudes and behaviors. Psychology turned out to be an experimental science while it is kneaded by the trends of positivism, empiricism, and materialism. (Schultz & Schultz, 2020)

Psychology is an interdisciplinary science that has more than fifty sub-fields. Human behaviors, attitudes, emotions, mental and developmental processes are explained through these fields. In Turkish society the importance of human psychology has been noticed since ancient times.

During the Middle Age of Europe the priests were responsible for healing of the mentally ill people. In the beginning, the priests treated the mentally ill people in a satisfactory manner. However, afterwards they believed that there was the devil in these people and began treating

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them rudely. A lot of mentally ill people were persecuted and killed in front of the public in the squares. Just at those times however during the Seljuk and Ottoman Empires, the problems of the mentally ill were trying to be solved. (Yıldırım, 2023)

There are many World-wide known scholars and physicians that come from Turkish culture, such as Avicenna, Ghazali and Farabi during the Seljuk and Ottoman Empires. Turkish culture was not far from the perspectives and practices about psychology. During the Ottomans, special departments in the hospitals and even special hospitals only for mentally ill persons have been built. The therapies by music and the sports have been applied in those hospitals. The development and the current status today have made a lot of progress recently. We have a lot of successful psychologists who are pioneers and experts in their fields.

During Seljuk and Ottoman Empires

In order to perceive other persons' attitudes and to learn how to benefit from some principles in their daily lives have always been important for people. Psychology presents us with some techniques for controlling animal and human attitudes and causing change if necessary. Turkish culture is familiar with the concept and applications of psychological support services. (Özkalp, 2002)

Mental health as well as body health has been cared about and paid attention to in Turkish society since eight. century. At the beginning of the 8.century, some special departments were established for people who are thought to have mental problems. At 9. century healing with music has been used. The famous scholar and physician Avicenna (980-1037) had evaluated mental problems as disorders of the brain. During the Seljuk and Ottoman Empires, some separate hospitals were built for patients who have mental disorders.

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Other than Avicenna, Farabi and Ghazali were also interested in psychology. The concept 'eye of the heart' belongs to Ghazali. The studies that Farabi have done about the concept of the absolute power of God and the spirit have also been considered to be included in the field of psychology.

The improvements after the Tanzimat(reorganization) Period had been accelerated because of the interactions with the West. French influence has been reverberated to psychology as well as daily life. At this period Hüseyin Cahit Yalçın (1875-1957) and Avni Basman (1887-1965) tried to present psychology.

In Turkey, the first lectures given began in 1868 in Dar-ül Fünün-i Osmani (today's Istanbul University). Psychology as a term has been first used in 1872 and the first book published about psychology is as well the same year. The title of the book was Ilm-i Ahval-i Ruh, in Ottoman language.

Afterwards in 1876 'Gayet-ül Beyan fi Hakikat-ul insan' was written and published by Yusuf Kemal. During this period, a lot of students have been

sent to Europe to get education in the new scientific areas. The names of the students that have been sent to get education in psychology and pedagogy are: İsmail Hakkı Baltacıoğlu, İbrahim Alaattin Gövsa, Mustafa Şekip Tunç, Sadrettin Celal Antel, Mustafa Rahmi Balaban and Halil Fikret Kanad. The students that are getting education from The Rousseau Institute are: Mustafa Şekip Tunç, İbrahim Alaattin Gövsa and Mustafa Rahmi Balaban.

At the time that these improvements were realized in Turkey, a psychology laboratory was being established and scientific studies had been pressed by Wilhelm Wundt. When it was 1911 Baha Tevfik (1884-1914) had written the first psychology book for psychology students. There was the definition and the subject of psychology, methodology and sub-fields of psychology in this book. Consciousness, memory, and motivation were also included in the book. And this book has served as a frame for Psychology as a science.

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In the year of 1907 Abdullah Cevdet translated Gustave Le Bon's 'Psychologie des Foule' to Turkish. During this period, a lot of foreign scientists' works have been translated and added to the field literature in Turkey. In WestWorld H.Bergson, A. Binet, E. Boutroux, E. Claperede, J. Dewey, E. Ebbing-Haus, S. Frued, H. Hoffding, W. James, T. Ribot were some of the scientists whose books had been translated.

Psychology in Turkey professionally is considered to begin in İstanbul University in the years of the one. World War. We may connect this beginning to the studies of the guest German professors. At this period, the Binet Intelligence Test was held in Turkey in 1915. After the World War, psychology had continued to be a lesson in the İstanbul University as part of philosophy by the management of Şekip Tunç. Ali Haydar Taner who was a pedagog taught experimental psychology at this period. Again at this period, psychology had entered as a lesson in teachers' school and a book had been pressed as a textbook. (Bozdemir, 2011)

After the Republic Period

One of the best social psychologists of the World, Muzaffer Şerif who had done his doctorate in Colombia University had given lectures in Gazi Eğitim Institute and Faculty of Dil Tarih Coğrafya. In 1945 because some of the lecturers had departed from Turkey, the lectures had stopped; however some guest American lecturers had continued to give lectures afterwards. (Bozdemir, 2011)

After 1950 in the Middle East University and Hacettepe University social psychology studies had been maintained. Ankara in this period had become a good center for psychology, for in a lot of good universities and institutions psychology lectures had been given. (Ankara University, Faculty of Language, History and Geography, Faculty of Education, Social Services Academy and School of Press and Broadcasting). (Bozdemir, 2011)

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In 1953-1954 Guidance and the techniques of guidance lectures were taught in Gazi Education Institute. In 1954 'Guidance in Schools' was published as a textbook. In 1955 Psychological Service Center and Guidance Investigation Service were established in Ankara. The National Education Councils had handled 'guidance' even if it was not in today's sense. During those years, 'Counseling Psychology' was included in the course schedule of the ODTU psychology department (Halmatov & Gülbahçe, 2020).

Professor Mümtaz Turhan became the principle of the Experimental Psychology Institute in 1960. He had two doctorates one from Frankfurt and the other from Cambridge. Professor Şekip Tunç and Sabri Esat Siyavuşgil were the other important psychologists of those years. (Yıldırım, 2023)

In 1965, the Education Psychology and Guidance department as an undergraduate program started in the faculty of education sciences of Ankara University. In 1966 the first master's program started in Hacettepe University. In 1970 a circular was published about the guidance services and their functions in the National Education Council. It has been reported clearly all the details about orientation, getting to know the student, observing, and evaluating the student. The Guidance and Psychological Counseling department had started in Hacettepe University in 1974. (Halmatov & Gülbahçe, 2020).

After the 1970's Bosphorus University was opened and it certainly contributed a lot to the development of the scientific areas in Turkey. In those years psychological research and investigations had gained speed. Academic studies were increased on an institutional basis. (Bozdemir, 2011)

A magazine named Psikoloji Çalışmaları (Psychology Studies) had been published in those years and supported all the students and the psychologists who needed to improve themselves. Professor Peterson organized this magazine that continued to be pressed. Afterwards the name of the magazine was changed to 'İstanbul University Experimental Studies' and nineteen volumes until 1985.

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In 1981 The National Education Council had decided to start undergraduate and master's programs about guidance and psychological counseling in the universities. Then in 1983, it was obligatory to have a center of psychological counseling and guidance in all the universities. In 1989, PDR-Association (Psychological Counseling and Guidance Association) was established. (Halmatov & Gülbahçe, 2020).

In recent years psychological counselors who work at the schools or psychological counseling centers have been educated and graduated from the guidance and psychological counseling programs of the universities. MEB (National Education Ministry) arranges the authorities and responsibilities of the persons who work in this area. However the development of this area has improved recently, it is still far from being sufficient qualitatively and quantitatively as well. Some of the important branches of psychology are clinical psychology, social psychology, experimental psychology, cognitive psychology, developmental psychology, health psychology, industrial and organizational psychology.

While trying to define the psychology area as a career, there are some difficulties that will be met. One of those difficulties is competition among the psychologists, psychiatrists and psychological counselors and guides. The mental health professionals have been discussing how to approach these problems since 1978. At this period, the outlines of the rights and the responsibilities of these professionals have been underlined. It is emphasized that psychologists may have work at the kindergartens, in the special education centers and elderly care homes. (Yıldırım, 2023).

One of the subjects that has been discussed in 1980's was the question of who would give education to the clinical psychologists. Topçu (1979), Savaşır (1980), Topçu and Kuzgun (1980) and Özer claimed that only psychologists would educate the psychologists however Gençtan (1980) put forward that in order for a clinical psychologist to apply therapy a psychiatrist (Yıldırım, 2023) should educate him.

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After these discussions in 1993, a legal property has been tried to be acquired to the definition of psychology. The Psychologists Association pioneered these studies. The responsibilities and the rights of the clinic psychologists and the other psychologists that are working on the other specialized areas were reviewed.

Psychologists Who Have Important Studies Recently

Erol Güngör is one of the good psychologists who has achieved important tasks. He graduated from the İstanbul University in 1961, advanced in social psychology and completed his doctorate degree in 1965. He translated some of the important psychology books to Turkish and contributed to the social psychology field a lot.

Hale Bacakoğlu, as a blind person, struggled and achieved to complete her bachelor's degree in psychology then, she has authored her thesis of doctorate on 'the children who have visual impairment.' She had worked to succeed in order for normal children and blind children to have education together.

Çiğdem Kağıtçıbaşı is one of the psychologists who has established social psychology in Turkey. She tried to remove Turkey from the American hegemony, however; contrary to her efforts, America was her best appreciator. More than two hundred scientific articles of her were published in the scientific press and fifty-eight books have been published. Generally her investigations were on developmental psychology, family, early childhood, parenthood, and the cultural development of people.

Muzaffer Şerif is again an important social psychologist. His 'Robbers Cave Experiments' are well known even in America. The parameters that have been used today on politics, racism and nationalism have been investigated and have been still used.

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Doğan Cüceloğlu has progressed in the area of developmental psychology, has given many seminars, and published more than forty articles in the scientific press. He had used to reach people from his youtube channel for years. Unfortunately, he died at the age of 83 in 2021.

Üstün Dökmen has a lot of poetry books, theater plays and scientific works as well. He is used to giving seminars in many unusual places of the world. He is the owner of a kindergarten chain named 'Küçük Şeyler.'

Ayten Zara completed her undergraduate and doctoral programs in England. She has worked on the 'Oasis Project' which is on the victims of domestic sexual violence.

She goes on to her studies in Bilgi University on family and society psychology.

Discussion and Conclusion

There are psychology undergraduate programs in 139 universities in Turkey. These programs last for four years. After undergraduate programs there are masters and doctoral programs on several branches such as Clinical psychology, social psychology, cognitive psychology, industrial and organizational psychology, developmental psychology, and educational psychology.

There are various kinds of mental health professionals such as psychologists, guides and psychological counselors, family and couple counselors and psychiatrists as well. Psychiatrists however are a subbranch of medicine. They have the right to prescribe medicine.

There are various kinds of therapies that are more often used in healing. These are cognitive and behavioral therapy, psychoanalysis, metacognitive therapy, EMDR (eye movement and desensitization and reprocessing therapy), Schema therapy, solution-focused therapy, acceptance and commitment therapy, family and couples therapy, dialectical behavior therapy,

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exposure therapy, mentalization therapy, psychodynamic therapy, animal-assisted therapy, Gottman therapy, Gestalt therapy, play therapy, existential therapy, art therapy, sand therapy, psychodrama and emotion-focused therapy are only some of them. In Turkey they all are used, however generally the psychologists use an eclectic type of therapy that would be convenient for the purpose and the one that is the most proper for the patient's situation. The psychologists treat many mental health problems such as anxiety disorders, depression, bipolar disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, schizophrenia, eating disorders, disruptive behavior and dissocial disorders, neurodevelopmental disorders, and trauma-related disorders.

Psychology in Turkey is still continuing to develop. There are many successful psychologists who have authored many important books, published many articles in science journals and given lectures in many good universities all around the world and applied various kinds of therapies and healed their patients. However there are still some shortcomings and deficiencies on this subject because the problems in this area are multidimensional, complicated, and intricate. Mental health professionals are face to face with these deficiencies. One of the problems in this area is that; even you complete the undergraduate program and even complete your master's and doctoral degrees, no one is ever ready to accept a patient. In the schools during the education the therapies are not taught to the students, so do the applications. Each one of the therapies must be learned outside from the educators, sometimes from the internet sites. The schools are not even theoretical. Practice already lacks. In schools only general information is given that is certainly not enough. One who plans and intends to be a good psychologist must get a lot of training after school by his own efforts and these are not cheap.

However despite all these problems, there are many young psychologists who challenge themselves to be skilled professionals and contribute to the psychology field in Turkey. Because psychology is a remarkably interesting scientific area that still needs more investigations, more research, and more observations.

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Limitations

This research is limited to the extent of the data in the world literature. The research is restricted to the research about the related subjects. It is limited to literature surveys.

Notices

Assessment: Internal and external advisors assessed this study.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declared no conflicts of interest in relation to this article.

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Ethical Declaration

This study aims to ensure that scientific research is made in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, respect for the findings and creations of others and aims to realize these principles in the field of related disciplines.

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